

E2.1 Use Case Definition Report

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Acronyms

UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
XR	Extended Reality
VR	Virtual Reality
Ai	Artificial Intelligence
SEC	Security
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
SLA	Service Level Agreements
SDN	Software Defined Networking
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
DOS	Denial of Service
MITM	Man in the Middle
QOS	Quality of Service
6DoF	6th Degree of Freedom

Executive Summary

The 6GENABLERS-SEC project is an research initiative that investigates the security, trust, and privacy in the complex ecosystem of 6G networks. The 6G environment is considered the next frontier in telecommunication and requires innovative and strong security measures. The principal objective is to augment the confidentiality, and dependability of these sophisticated networks through the utilisation of cutting-edge technologies and methodologies like programmable data planes, strict access controls, and secure data communication. This deliverable provides an overview of the holo-portation use case in the context of the 6G environment. The utilisation of holo-portation, which is a method of communication that utilises augmented and virtual reality, represents a substantial innovation compared to traditional communication technologies, less immersive for the user. This introduces unique obstacles in the areas of privacy and security. The present report thoroughly examines the characteristics and functions of holocommunication and aptly recognizes the vulnerabilities like tempering of user data, disruption of the service, and eavesdropping of communication in its privacy and trust features, which may impede adoption. Moreover, the report elucidates the intricacies of the interactions and workflows entailed in the holo-portation process, thereby clarifying the intricacies of this communication technology. The report encompasses an end-to-end perspective of the use case, ranging from specifying the requirements essential for enabling secure and dependable holo-portation to outlining key performance indicators for evaluating the successful attainment of these requirements. The report presents an explanation of the 6GENABLERS-SEC initiative, elucidating its aims of devising a resilient trust and privacy framework, putting in place inventive protective measures, and implementing efficacious security controls to address the distinctive exigencies of the 6G context. The report thoroughly outlines the threats and mitigation strategies related to trust and privacy, highlighting their crucial significance in the success of holocommunication. The text expounds upon the functional requirements that must be fulfilled in order to surmount potential hindrances, thereby facilitating the smooth incorporation of this state-of-the-art communication technology into the 6G domain. The Report presents a validation set of requirements that delineates the project's specifications, prerequisites for testbeds, and a proficient assessment methodology. The aforementioned constituents furnish the mechanism for gauging the operational efficacy via precisely delineated key performance indicators. This report of the 6GENABLERS-SEC project provides a comprehensive analysis of the fundamental elements and possible obstacles of holo-portation within the framework of 6G.

1 Introduction

The 6G-Enablers-SEC initiative is currently undertaking a research project that focuses on the security, trust, and privacy aspects of 6G networks. The primary objective of this initiative is to establish a comprehensive trust and privacy framework, identify and mitigate vulnerabilities like eavesdropping, side channel attacks, Man in the Middle attacks and many more and to devise sophisticated security mechanisms like programmable data planes, proposing strict access controls mechanisms, and privacy aware orchestration. The safeguarding of the physical layer against potential security threats such as jamming and spoofing is a priority, and this is achieved through the utilisation of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence and radio frequency fingerprinting. This project delves into the practical aspects of deploying security measures across various network components, with a focus on optimising performance through the utilisation of cutting-edge technologies. The suggested comprehensive strategy aims to significantly improve the dependability and credibility of upcoming wireless communication systems.

The use-case definition offers the context for understanding the actual application of the project's deliverables, which are largely focused on ensuring that holographic communication is both safe and dependable. The use-case serves to steer the creation of protocols, systems, and tools required to create a secure and resilient platform while respecting user privacy and keeping ethical standards. It also helps to highlight how upcoming technologies, such as edge computing and artificial intelligence, may be used to improve the platform's performance and security. This can be a very useful thing to know. The use case in issue is centred on the incorporation of holoportation and virtual reality (VR) services, both of which make use of the increased capabilities offered by 6G technology in order to permit communication that is immersive, safe, and in real time. This covers both business holo-conferences as well as a wide range of personal contacts, all of which are made possible by connection with ultra-low latency.

The ever-increasing desire for immersive communication techniques, in conjunction with the simultaneous necessity to guarantee data security and user privacy, is the impetus for the development of this use case. In this day and age of distributed teamwork, the ability to communicate in a safe and efficient manner while maintaining a real-time component is of the utmost importance. The combination of modern 6G capabilities, together with built-in security features and functionality that has been boosted by artificial intelligence, promises to give unmatched levels of immersion, interactivity, and safety. As a result, the use case represents a big step forward in satisfying the expanding demands of distant communication and collaboration while also protecting user privacy and data.

1.1 Structure of the document

This report outlines a strategy aimed at conducting an analysis of the holo-portation use case within the dynamic context of 6G networks. The report has been crafted with the aim of enhancing the credibility, confidentiality, and dependability of these networks. This study methodically examines the domain of Holocommunication,

analysing its contextual background, practical implementation, and inherent hazards, thereby illuminating the shortcomings in security, privacy and trust features.

Chapter 2 of this study delves into the strategic objectives of the project, which serves as a central aspect of the investigation. The aforementioned aspects encompass the establishment of a resilient framework for trust and privacy, the generation of inventive protective measures, and the implementation of security controls with superior performance. This comprehensive overview not only establishes the context for the subsequent detailed examination of the holocommunication use case but also demonstrates the project's potential for transformation.

The third chapter of the report performs a comprehensive evaluation of the potential threats associated with the holocommunication UC that has been implemented on the 6G platform. The analysis primarily emphasises the aspects of security, privacy, and trust. The project requirements are driven by the identified shortcomings, which necessitate the implementation of countermeasures to mitigate the associated risks and threats. The report suggests a series of measures to tackle the aforementioned challenges, with the goal of reducing the identified risks and guaranteeing the comprehensive security, privacy, and reliability of the holocommunication UC on the 6G platform. The aforementioned measures comprise both technical and operational facets, which include the implementation of sturdy encryption protocols, fortification of the network infrastructure, imposition of stringent access controls, and deployment of privacy-amplifying mechanisms.

Chapter 4 of the report presents a validation methodology aimed at evaluating the project's efficiency and operational effectiveness. The methodology involves a structured evaluation of the specifications and the Key Performance Indicators. The chapter underscores the significance of establishing pivotal metrics as foundational benchmarks for assessing the project. The metrics have been formulated with the purpose of evaluating the project's compliance with its stipulated requirements, thereby verifying the attainment of the intended goals.

In Section 5, In the conclusion of the report, the importance of the 6GENABLERS-SEC project is emphasised. This sets the stage for understanding the project's wider meanings and effects. It shows how important this project is for driving creativity, and paving the way for future improvements in information technology.

The "Use Case Definition" report provides a comprehensive analysis of the holocommunication use case, a thorough validation strategy, and a detailed project overview. It serves as a crucial reference for comprehending the innovative 6GENABLERS-SEC project. The report provides a comprehensive overview of the 6GENABLERS-SEC project, highlighting its objectives, the intricacies of the holocommunication use case, and the wide-ranging implications of the project. This underscores the considerable potential of the project in driving progress in the telecommunications sector.

1.2 Structure of Tables:

The report details a comprehensive threat analysis of potential risks associated with Holocommunication, utilising the STRIDE method. The initial table 1 presents 6GENABLERS platform requirements. Table 2 is utilised to identify and document the potential threats, along with their corresponding impacts on the system. Subsequently, Table 3 presented our suggested countermeasures to address each identified risk, furnishing an all-encompassing strategy to mitigate those threats. The report provided a comprehensive analysis of the functional and non-functional requirements of the Holocommunication system in Table 5 and 6 respectively. Going forward, we have discussed the essential requirements for Security, Trust, and Privacy in Holocommunication in Table 6. The mentioned threats were linked with their corresponding countermeasures in a separate set of tables, thereby illustrating the interconnections among the identified threats, the corresponding countermeasures, and the underlying prerequisites., as well as the associated key performance indicators (KPIs) in Table 7. The data is compiled in a tabular format to offer a comprehensive understanding of the anticipated outcomes of the system and the criteria that will be employed to assess its efficacy.

1.3 Target Audience

The document provides an in-depth understanding of the project's objectives, core functionalities, and potential industry impact. Concurrently, it serves the technical audience involved in the project by offering crucial technical insights, addressing foreseeable challenges, and suggesting appropriate mitigation strategies. Furthermore, the document takes into account potential users, such as service providers and end-users, ensuring their perspectives are incorporated. This multifaceted approach aligns the report with the standards expected by the European Union, fostering a comprehensive understanding of the 6GENABLERS-SEC project for all relevant parties.

1.4 Requirements definition and encoding

The requirements for the 6GENABLERS-SEC project are classified accordingly:

- Functional requirements (F): They draw the features that must be accomplished by a system.
- Non-functional requirements (NF): They explicit criteria used to evaluate the quality of the system operation.

To adopt an incremental approach during the systems' design and development, a prioritisation mechanism based on the MoSCoW method [1] has been employed. This technique categorises requirements into four priority groups: MUST have, SHOULD have, COULD have, and WON'T have, each representing a different level of importance:

- **MUST:** These requirements are deemed necessary to the achievement of the framework objectives. They must be designed, implemented and verified to meet the project objective.
- **SHOULD:** The requirements labelled in this category are important to meet the project's end, but not strictly mandatory. Their implementation as part of the framework are recommended.
- **COULD:** These requirements contribute to the project objective and are desirable, but not mandatory. They can be considered for implementation as an extra effort.
- **WON'T:** These requirements have been concurred to be least critical for the project execution. They are deemed to be ignored during the timeframe of the project execution and potentially be considered for future activities.

Based on the structure of the report, the requirements for the 6GENABLERS-SEC project will be identified as follows:

- An ID with the format SEC-XX for functional requirements and SEC-NF-XX for non-functional requirements uniquely identifies the requirements coming from the 6GENABLERS-SEC project (6GENABLERS Specifications table).
- The requirements specific to the Holocommunication use case are identified as HOL-UC-XX.
- The <topic> identifier represents specific categories to help identify each constraint:
 - **HOL: Holo communication**
 - **CTR: Countermeasure**
 - **T-X: Threat ID**
 - **SEC: Security Requirements**
 - **TP: Trust & Privacy**
 - **PHYS: Physical**
 - **DP: Dataplane**
- The XX represents a progressive number associated with the specific requirement.

2 Overview of 6GENABLERS Trust, Privacy & Security for 6G

In this section, we provide a brief overview of the 6GENABLERS “Trust, Privacy & Security for 6G” (6GENABLERS-SEC) project, and issue some initial requirements. We describe in the first subsection the general objectives of the project, and analysis in the second time specific technical objectives.

2.1 Project objectives

The primary focus of this project is centred on the examination of trust and privacy structures in the context of 6G communications technology. The ultimate goal is to establish a security framework that is characterised by its strength, durability, and dependability. The 6GENABLERS-SEC initiative places emphasis on three primary domains, namely the establishment of dependable trust and privacy frameworks, the introduction of novel security mechanisms and techniques, and the creation of functional prototypes for empirical evaluation and implementation. The aforementioned components have been formulated with the intention of tackling the nascent obstacles and hazards that are linked to 6G networks, in accordance with the project's progressive outlook. The 6GENABLERS-SEC initiative is characterised by its capacity to promptly detect potential hazards, bolstered by exceptionally efficient security measures. The capability to identify and mitigate threats in real time represents a significant advancement in the realm of 6G technology. The 6GENABLERS-SEC initiative embodies a novel and forward-thinking strategy towards ensuring security in 6G technology, promoting the creation of 6G systems that are secure, reliable, and prioritise privacy. This undertaking not only enhances the dependability and robustness of 6G infrastructure but also reinforces user faith and assurance in this nascent technology.

To enact this vision, the 6GENABLERS-SEC project revolves around five main objectives:

To define and prototype a 6G system-level architecture with guarantees for trust, privacy, reliability and security; leveraging techniques to preserve the end-user privacy and assess the trust on the involved systems, whilst providing high-performing, non-disruptive security mechanisms and controls that mitigate detected attacks and aim at preserving reliability in the involved systems.

This objective oversees the preparation of a system architecture compatible suited for deployment in 6G environments, compatible with the foreseen mobile network infrastructures and permitting the operation of 6G telecommunication applications. This architecture will permit the preservation of end-user privacy by overseeing the platform

configuration. One lever relates to the trust evaluation of the components, interfaces and infrastructure supporting the usage of the application, contributing the end-user privacy and the overall security of the environment. The reliability of the platform is converted from a cybersecurity perspective, by proposing the usage of programmable resources to enforce security control to mitigate attacks. The programmability is to be defined in the system architecture, and be compatible with the operated 6G application, with a limited impact on traditional telecommunication SLA.

To validate the 6GENABLERS architecture and solution with the relevant technical KPIs focused on the trust, privacy and security enabling techniques, as well as with a 6G vertical use case such as real-time multi-party holo-portation (i.e. holographic tele-transportation) technology.

This objective defines the baseline of the evaluation, which should cover both (i) the contribution to the security, trust and privacy objectives but also (ii) its impact on the normal operation on a telecommunication application. The suggested application relates to the real-time multi-party holo-portation technology. The evaluation is suggested to be in priority quantitative, via the evaluation of measurable key performance indicators (KPIs). Additionally, a qualitative evaluation sanctioning the effective implementation of requirements can be considered.

To ensure the long-term success of the project through standardisation and dissemination in scientific, industrial, and commercial fora, and by contributing to relevant open source communities & SDOs also exploring synergies with other EU initiatives and projects.

This objective relates to the dissemination & exploitation objective of the project. Technically speaking, this objective stems on multiple perspective:

- The delivered architecture and interface should be open, standard or standardizable, to ensure the sustainability of the developed work after the project's end.
- The delivered components should comply with a level of maturity allowing, if pertinent, their opening to Open Source communities and their usage after the project ends.

To define and prototype a Trust & Privacy Framework that can ensure a trustworthy 6G system, assessing the trust on the involved systems and ensuring the confidentiality and privacy of the users communicating.

In this objective review the expected outcome of the project, i.e. the design, development of an architecture aligned with 6G telecommunication network objectives, serving the incentive of innocuity and privacy preservation of user communicating.

This objective draws several requirements on the platform.

First, this requirement draws an explicit requirement on trust evaluation on the components in interaction in the architecture. This could relate either the infrastructure nodes, compound of the data plane, but also service instances supporting a 6G application.

Second, confidentiality can be interpreted both in terms of data and metadata circulating on the network. They can either relate to (i) the services supporting the application or (ii) to the platform component itself.

In the first case, the proposed framework should propose features to support the application's privacy while, in the second case, the framework design should be evaluated to incorporate security objectives.

To design and implement (i) novel security mechanisms to protect the network through dynamic detection and mitigation of attacks; and (ii) high-performing, non-disruptive and efficient security controls to provide security by design, enforce proper separation of concerns per plane and preserve the reliability in the involved systems.

This objective contemplates the design of deployable enablers serving the detection and mitigation of security threats, to ensure their innocuity. Those mechanisms should be differentiated in nature and function to cover multiple planes of the foreseen 6G architecture, such application plane, control plane and data plane as per a non-explicit requirement relating to the supervision and management of those mechanisms.

2.2 Functionalities of the 6GENABLERS-SEC platform

In the previous subsection, we analysed the 6GENABLERS-SEC objectives. Based on this analysis, we identify several functional requirements from the 6GENABLERS platform. This primary analysis is important as this will cater to the possible countermeasures tackling responding to assessed security threats.

Table 1 6GENABLERS Functional Requirements

Req ID	Requirement	Priority (MoSCoW)
TP-01	The trust and privacy framework in 6GENABLERS-SEC allows the specification of a trust model accounting for network environment, actors and stakeholders, platform components and layers.	Must
TP-02	The trust model could be applicable to the network data plane	Could
TP-03	The privacy policy evaluation and enforcement has to account for posture of network segments, the vertical services, platform components and infrastructure.	Must
TP-04	The identity management and authentication should account for the identity of the network users and contribute to trust.	Should
PHYS-01	The physical attacks are to be mitigated based on elicited threat context, current posture of the communication modes.	Must
PHYS-02	Cognitive radio strategy can be considered for physical threat mitigation.	Could
PHYS-03	Security mechanisms shall be designed to ensure transmission of information to legit transmitter, and minimise information to untrusted one.	Must
DP-01	The security mechanisms are deployable on the network dataplane	Must
DP-02	The security mechanisms should adapt to different trust models and posture	Should
DP-03	The security mechanisms could leverage cryptography feature	Could
DP-04	The security mechanisms on the data plan have to be controlled.	Must
DP-05	Security mechanisms may leverage technology such as SDN, NG-SDN and NFV as enabling technique for programmability.	Should

3 Holocommunication Use-case Description and Analysis

The advent of 6G networks presents a multitude of novel applications, among which Holocommunication stands out as particularly important. This section offers an in-depth analysis of the security validation of Holocommunication in 6G networks, accompanied by a thorough contextualization and description of the use-case. Holocommunication, which is widely considered as the upcoming mode of communication, employs the technique of holographic projection to facilitate an engaging and instantaneous exchange of information. The integration of this innovative technology with the high-speed, minimal delay capabilities of 6G networks holds the promise of a comprehensive overhaul of our digital engagements. Nevertheless, it is imperative to acknowledge the security challenges that are linked with such technological advancements. This section presents an overview of the use case, including its description and context, as well as the deployment strategy for the effective and secure implementation of Holocommunication in 6G networks.

3.1 Context

Holographic teleportation has emerged as a state-of-the-art technological innovation in immersive conferencing applications, providing users with an experience that enables them to navigate freely within a virtual environment. Holographic teleportation is poised to become a pivotal element of the upcoming 6G technology, with the capacity to transform numerous sectors such as gaming, entertainment, education, healthcare, and tourism. This technology offers the potential to enable immersive and interactive communication services, thereby revolutionising these industries.

Specifically, holoportation could provide transformative benefits in various sectors:

1. **Remote Collaboration:** Holoportation has the potential to facilitate a more immersive and authentic collaborative experience by allowing remote team members to engage in 3D virtual interaction, thereby replicating the sensation of coexisting in the same physical environment.
2. **Distance Learning:** The utilisation of holoportation technology has the potential to augment distance learning by enabling students to participate in classes and interact with instructors and fellow students within a three-dimensional virtual setting, thereby promoting heightened engagement and immersion.
3. **Virtual Reality:** Holoportation can help make virtual reality more intense and interesting by making it easier for users to connect with their surroundings in a way that feels more real.
4. **Telemedicine:** Holoportation has the potential to enhance the delivery of remote healthcare services by facilitating physicians to conduct consultations with patients in a more personalised and effective manner, akin to an in-person interaction.
5. **Social Interactions:** Holoportation can help people talk to each other in a more natural and personal way, no matter where they are in the world. This can make people feel less alone and isolated.

In order to achieve widespread adoption and establish trust among users, Extended Reality (XR) services must prioritise ethics, privacy, security, and safety. Additionally, it is important for these services to provide satisfactory Service Level Agreements (SLAs) to mitigate potential social, economic, and legal implications. Metaverse-like services have the potential to serve as a powerful medium for conducting realistic, natural, and trustworthy meetings between remote users across various entertainment and professional domains.

The 6GENABLERS-SEC platform is set to incorporate HoloMIT as a significant use case. HoloMIT is a modular platform that facilitates real-time holographic communication between multiple parties situated in different locations. This technology is a pioneering development on a global scale. The adoption of HoloMIT is expected to enhance the capabilities of the 6GENABLERS-SEC platform. The source of this information is [2] and [3]. The technology in question is considered disruptive as it facilitates human-cyber-physical services. It is anticipated that this technology will serve as the next-generation medium for social interaction and collaboration, with significant implications across various verticals such as entertainment, culture, training, virtual tourism, meetings, and eHealth.

In contrast to the majority of multi-user extended reality (XR) platforms that utilise artificial avatars, HoloMIT offers authentic volumetric user self and peer representations that are captured in real-time. This feature enhances the credibility of communications and facilitates a resilient identity management system. In contrast to the limited number of existing volumetric video capture systems, HoloMIT utilises inexpensive and portable capture sensors and adheres to standard-compliant technologies and formats, thereby enhancing both interoperability and dependability.

The visual representation depicted in Figure 1 illustrates various scenarios and applications facilitated by HoloMIT. These include a shared XR environment accommodating four users, some of whom possess complete 3D Point Cloud representations while others have more restricted 2D-video avatar representations. Additionally, the figure portrays two holographic users teleported into a virtual museum, as well as two holographic users participating in a virtual meeting.

XR and Metaverse-like services face numerous obstacles and difficulties with regards to security, privacy, ethics, and reliability. In contrast, it is expected that upcoming XR services such as HoloMIT will undergo a transformation towards modularization, virtualization, and utilisation of the advanced features of intelligent network and orchestration techniques. This includes the virtualization and instantiation of virtualized network/media functions over the Cloud Continuum, as depicted in the proposed architecture illustrated in Figure 1. The objective is to enhance the adaptability, scalability, and interoperability of the services in question. However, this project presents additional obstacles in the areas of trustworthiness, security, privacy, and reliability, particularly in the context of open, widespread, and cross-domain implementations.

Figure 1 Evolution roadmap of HoloMIT and its relevance to 6G-Enablers

Under the initiative of 6GENABLERS-SEC, we are taking comprehensive steps to ensure a robust and secure environment for the functioning of HOLO-MIT. The establishment of a robust trust and privacy framework lies at the heart of our approach, enabling users to safely interact within the network with full confidence in the privacy and security of their data. In parallel, we are employing advanced encryption techniques for the secure transmission of data, ensuring the integrity and confidentiality of information while maintaining respect for user privacy. In addition, we have implemented rigorous security protocols at the physical level, reinforcing our network architecture and enhancing its ability to withstand potential risks. Our approach is also guided by the principle of pervasive security, which has been seamlessly integrated into all aspects of the network. This all-encompassing security layer covers network operations, software, and infrastructure components from edge to core, allowing us to proactively identify and address potential vulnerabilities. By implementing these tactics, 6GENABLERS-SEC is propelling the advancement of 6G technologies towards improved accessibility and dependability, guaranteeing a secure progression of these crucial technologies.

3.2 HoloMIT Application Presentation

The immersive holo-conference system comprises a sophisticated framework of interlinked technologies that aim to establish a lifelike and interactive virtual milieu for its users.

The initial stage of the process entails configuring the environment, which encompasses the installation of 3D video capturing equipment, including cameras and

sensors. Users may opt to use VR headsets or glasses in order to achieve a fully immersive experience. The utilisation of these devices is imperative, as they serve as the fundamental hardware foundation for the acquisition and immersion within the simulated environment. Subsequently, the calibration phase for the user ensues. The instruments are calibrated to employ depth sensing, LiDAR, and computer vision techniques for the purpose of mapping the user's surroundings. The aforementioned process proficiently captures the user's physical environment and converts it into a digital representation. The system has the capability to eliminate the background, thereby enabling the user to be situated in the communal virtual realm devoid of any undesired elements from their actual surroundings.

Upon completion of the calibration process, the system transitions to the phase of real-time capture and transmission. HoloMIT technology enables the capture of users' physical appearance and movements in real-time through the use of 3D volumetric video, resulting in a highly detailed digital representation. The aforementioned information is subsequently conveyed to the holo-conference platform through the utilisation of 6G network connectivity. 6G's high speed and low latency render it a suitable option for this particular application, as it facilitates the instantaneous transmission of substantial amounts of data.

Upon transmission, the data is subjected to subsequent stages of processing and rendering. The platform undertakes the compression and correction of volumetric video for data transmission, a pivotal measure that guarantees the optimal utilisation of bandwidth while preserving the video's quality. Subsequently, the system proceeds to generate the analysed three-dimensional footage within a communal virtual environment, thereby fabricating realistic representations of user avatars. The avatars function as the users' digital representations within the virtual realm, mimicking the actions and movements of their physical counterparts in real-time.

Upon entering the virtual environment, individuals participate in a fully-engaging holographic conferencing encounter. The use of lifelike avatars and instantaneous communication facilitates interactions that are perceived as authentic and instinctive. The system enhances the immersive experience by incorporating spatial audio and haptic feedback, which contribute to a greater sense of presence and realism that surpasses the impact of visual stimuli. This establishes a milieu that not only enables intercommunication but also nurtures collaboration among the users. The system offers comprehensive tools for managing and controlling sessions with a high level of reliability. Individuals have the capability to establish, extend invitations to additional participants, and distribute holo conferences. Furthermore, the platform facilitates the moderation of comments, the regulation of access, and the monitoring of user interactions. The aforementioned characteristics guarantee a secure and well-structured digital milieu, which enables users to concentrate on their interactions without being concerned about technical or logistical impediments.

To summarise, the immersive holo-conference system is a complex integration of various technologies that operate in conjunction to produce a lifelike, engaging, and easily navigable virtual setting.

3.3 Gap analysis for Trust, Privacy & Security in Holocommunication in 6G networks

The following table shows a risk assessment of privacy trust that is carried out on Holo Communication. The objective of this analysis is to evaluate possible risks to confidentiality and trust among the context of holocommunication technology. The assessment relies on the STRIDE threat evaluation methodology, which offers a systematic framework for recognizing and alleviating risks in computer systems and communication protocols.

The STRIDE threat assessment methodology is a widely used approach for identifying and categorising potential security threats. It involves analysing a system or application for potential threats in six key areas: Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denial of Service, and Elevation of Privilege. By systematically evaluating these areas, the STRIDE methodology can help organisations better understand and mitigate potential security risks. The STRIDE threat assessment methodology is a well-established framework that is commonly employed to evaluate security threats in computer systems and network communications. The classification of possible hazards is divided into six discrete groupings, namely Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denial of Service, and Elevation of Privilege. Through the assessment of risks based on these classifications, entities can enhance their comprehension of the possible susceptibilities in their frameworks and establish suitable safeguards.

Actors can be defined as individuals who perform a role or character in a theatrical production, film, television show, or other forms of entertainment media.

Within the scope of this risk assessment, the term "actors" pertains to the entities or individuals who are engaged in holocommunication. The holocommunication infrastructure can be interacted with by both system components and users, who may be considered as actors in this context. The individuals who perform in the system assume distinct roles and exhibit diverse degrees of access and authorisation. Comprehending the actors is imperative for evaluating potential hazards to confidentiality and confidence, as their conduct and motives can influence the security of the holocommunication environment.

Table 2 Threats Analysis

Threat ID	Component	Class (STRIDE)	Impacted assets	Description	Criticality	Probability
HOL-TI-01	3D Video Capturing Equipment	Tampering with Data	3D volumetric data	Unauthorised alteration of captured 3D data could distort users' digital representations	High	Moderate
HOL-TI-02	3D Video Capturing Equipment	Information Disclosure	3D volumetric data	Unauthorised access to raw 3D data could leak sensitive user communication	High	High
HOL-T2-01	VR Devices	Denial of Service	User immersion experience	Disabling VR devices could disrupt the immersive experience, making the service unavailable.	High	low
HOL-T3-01	Depth Sensing	Spoofing Identity	User environment mapping	Feeding falsified data to these systems could misrepresent a user's physical surroundings.	High	Moderate
HOL-T3-02	Depth Sensing	Tampering with Data	User environment mapping	Altering the data from these systems could distort the digital representation of a user's environment.	High	Moderate
HOL-T4-01	Real-time Capture	Information	User physical	Unprotected transmission of	Very High	High

	and Transmission Mechanism	Disclosure	appearance and movements data	this data could leak highly sensitive user information.		
HOL-T5-01	Data Processing and Rendering Systems	Tampering with Data	Processed volumetric video data	Altering processed data could distort the final rendered environment and user avatars.	High	High
HOL-T5-02	Data Processing and Rendering Systems	Information Disclosure	Processed volumetric video data	Unauthorised access to processed data could leak sensitive details about the virtual environment and user avatars.	High	High
HOL-T5-03	Data Processing and Rendering Systems	Dos Spoofing	Disruption, Impersonation	Disruptions caused due to Dos attack to process, and impersonation could take place by spoofing identity	High	High
HOL-T6-01	Virtual Environment Generation System	Tampering with Data	Virtual environment, user avatars	Unwanted alterations in the virtual environment or user avatars could damage the user experience.	High	Moderate
HOL-T6-02	Virtual Environment Generation System	Information Disclosure	Virtual environment, user avatars	Unauthorised access to the system's generated data could leak details about the virtual environment and user avatars.	High	High

HOL-T7-01	Session Management	Elevation of Privilege	Session controls	Gaining unauthorised access to session controls could allow a malicious actor to manipulate or disrupt a session.	Very High	Moderate
HOL-T7-02	Session Management	Spoofing Identity	Session controls	Impersonating a session administrator could allow a malicious actor to take control of a session.	High	Moderate

3.4 Countermeasure propositions

This section outlines a collection of functional requirements that have been deduced from the threat analysis carried out for ensuring privacy trust in holocommunication. The stated requirements have been formulated with the aim of minimising the potential threats and establishing a solid basis for the creation of a holocommunication system that is both secure and reliable. The description of each requirement along with the component will be provided along with an explanation, emphasising its importance in mitigating particular threats and susceptibilities. The integration of these functional requirements into the design and implementation of holocommunication technology enables organisations to establish a secure and privacy-conscious communication ecosystem.

Table 3 Countermeasures for Detected Risks

Countermeasure ID	Component	Covered Threat Id	Description
HOL-CTR-01	3D Video Capturing Equipment	HOL-T1-01 HOL-R1-02	Framework allows for 3D video capturing equipment to securely connect to the 6G network while protecting against unauthorized access and tampering.
HOL-CTR-02	VR Devices	HOL-T2-01	Failover and Recovery systems,

		HOL-T2-02	Build-in jamming and spoofing detection at the physical layer to maintain the service for VR Devices
HOL-CTR-03	VR Devices	HOL-T3-01 HOL-T3-02	AI and RF-fingerprinting techniques to authenticate the signals and data inputs.
HOL-CTR-04	Real-time Capture and Transmission Mechanism	HOL-T4-01	Robust security controls for data transmission and enforcing traffic management policies.
HOL-CTR-05	Data Processing and Rendering Systems	HOL-T5-01 HOL-T5-02	Advanced cryptographic methods for data in transit High-performance security controls would ensure data integrity checks
HOL-CTR-06	Virtual Environment Generation System	HOL-T6-01 HOL-T6-02	Ensuring strict access control for users & resources, Data validation for User Interactions & User Input
HOL-CTR-07	Session Management Tools	HOL-T7-01 HOL-T7-02	Multi-factor authentication methods and role-based access control strategies.

4 Requirements Elicitation and validation strategy

The section presents a thorough method for evaluating the performance and effectiveness of the HoloMIT system. It covers the diverse parts of requirements elicitation and validation, encompassing the separation of functional and non-functional requirements, particular requirements for security, trust, and privacy in holocommunication, along with the validation procedure and crucial performance indicators to ensure the efficacy of the executed approaches.

4.1 Functional Requirements

Functional requirements pertain to a collection of specifications that delineate the operations that a system must possess the ability to execute, as well as the manner in which those operations ought to be executed. The specifications outline the requisite functions, features, and capabilities that a system or software application must possess in order to meet the demands of its users.

The tabular presentation comprehensively outlines all the essential particulars that are imperative for providing an optimal holoportation encounter in relation to both its operation and quality.

Table 4 Functional Requirements

Req. Id	Functional Requirement	Description	Priority (MoSCoW)
HOL-UC-1	Holoportation experience	An end user should have an experience that visually and acoustically allows them to perceive and understand the other participants' body language expressions.	Should
HOL-UC-2	Holoportation content visual quality	The virtual character representation must be detailed enough to allow for the recognition of facial expressions	Must

HOL-UC-3	Holoportation content	The representations of the rendered characters, inside the virtual space of holoportation, must be able to retarget their gaze according to the end-user's viewpoint. The representations of the rendered pre-rigged characters, inside the virtual space of holoportation, must be able to retarget pointing gestures	Must
HOL-UC-4	Active watch	The end user inside the virtual space of holoportation must be able to become a character within the storyline that is being projected	Must
HOL-UC-5	Movement	The end user inside the virtual space of holoportation must be able to move in 6DoF	Must
HOL-UC-6	Derived actions	The end-user's actions inside the virtual space of holoportation must lead to changes in the storyline that is being projected	Must
HOL-UC-7	Pattern recognition interaction	The holoportation platform must support multi modal pattern recognition mechanics for changing the storyline according to user's choices	Must
HOL-UC-8	Pointing interaction	The holoportation must be able to recognize pointing gestures of end users and change the storyline accordingly	Must
HOL-UC-9	Speech interaction	The holoportation platform must be able to recognize the speech of end users and change the storyline accordingly	Must

HOL-UC-10	Interactive character	The system should integrate and use interactive character animation	Should
HOL-UC-11	Configuration	The holoportation platform orchestration component must manage sessions where at least 2 end users participate in a virtual space. The holoportation platform orchestration component should support at least two parallel sessions	Must
HOL-UC-12	Holoportation scenario	The holoportation platform might allow 10 end users to simultaneously be in the same virtual space	Wont
HOL-UC-13	Latency	The Holoportation platform must achieve an end to end (capture to projection) latency that is lower than 100 ms.	Must
HOL-UC-14	Compression	The Holoportation platform SHOULD support point cloud compression of arbitrary topology and be able to achieve a compression ratio of up to 1:30 for textured mesh (3D geometry and textures) content	Should
HOL-UC-15	Synchronisation	The Holoportation play-out component's native player SHOULD support synchronisation between different input formats with less than 100 ms of delay	Should

4.2 Non-Functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements refer to a collection of specifications that establish the traits, features, and properties of a given system or software application, in contrast to its precise functional capacities. The previous requirements are applicable to the overall efficiency, excellence, and user-friendliness of the system or software applications, as opposed to its specific functionalities and characteristics.

The non-functional requirements of the use-case are listed as follows:

Table 5 Non- Functional Requirement

Req. Id	Non-Functional Requirement	Description	Priority (MoSCoW)
HOL-UC-NF-1	Scalability	The implementation of the use case should be scalable and allow for the automatic admission of multiple concurrent AR users/sessions/slices without modifying the architecture.	Must
HOL-UC-NF-2	Interoperability	The setup of the use case should be interoperable with any type of user device/AR kit	Must
HOL-UC-NF-3	Modularity	The implementation should be modular to a great extent in such a way the upgrade of one component can be independently done without affecting the other components.	Should
HOL-UC-NF-4	Quality assessment	The Holoportation platform SHOULD be able to evaluate the expected quality of experience according to the objective metrics	Must

HOL-UC-NF-5	Content visual quality	The Holoportation platform MUST support playback of end-user's representation of at least 960x540 pixels	Could
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4.3 Requirements for Security, Trust and Privacy in Holocommunication

The functional requirements to be executed applies to the particular abilities and characteristics that must be included in the system or technology's design and development. The implementation of these functional requirements are crucial in ensuring a secure and trustworthy holocommunication environment in the context of security, trust, and privacy for 6G. It outlines the necessary components and functionalities that must be in place to achieve this goal.

Holocommunication refers to the use of holographic technologies to facilitate immersive communication. This technology enables individuals to interact with each other in real-time, regardless of their physical location, as if they were present in the same room. In order to ensure security, trust, and privacy in holocommunication, it is important to consider the following implementation functional requirements for 6G.

Table 6 Holocommunication: Key Requirements for Security, Trust, and Privacy

Req. Id	Requirement	Countermeasure ID.	Priority (MoSCoW)
SEC-01	Robust data security framework, using a combination of policy and technical controls to safeguard data in transit.	HOL-CTR-01	Must
SEC-02	Prioritise device and system integrity, deploying protective measures against unauthorised access and threats.	HOL-CTR-02 HOL-CTR-03	Could
SEC-03	Traffic management to improve data transfer by prioritising Quality of Service (QoS) and proactively addressing security issues.	HOL-CTR-04	Should
SEC-04	Advanced	HOL-CTR-05	Should

	cryptographic solutions, ensuring secure data transmission		
SEC-05	Secure virtual environments, protecting them from cyber threats and maintaining secure access.	HOL-CTR-06	Must
SEC-06	Session management approach ensures user sessions are protected from unauthorised access or breaches	HOL-CTR-07	Must

4.4 Validation and Key performance indicators

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are crucial for measuring the performance and effectiveness of each functional requirement that has been taken. By utilising predefined fit criteria, these indicators enable us to assess the effectiveness of each function in achieving its intended outcome in a quantitative manner. System functioning can be evaluated by analysing various factors. This analysis can provide valuable insights into the system's overall working, including areas of strength and areas that may require further attention or improvement. By adopting a data-driven approach, decision-making is based on reliable evidence, enabling the implementation of more precise and efficient strategies for ongoing system enhancement.

Table 7 Key Performance Indicators

KPI. Id	KPI Name	Req. origin	Fit criteria (KPI)
KPI-01	End-to-End Communication Delay	SEC-01, SEC-03	End-to-end delay in the communication between two distinct interlocutors is to be low
KPI-02	Security & privacy enforcement configuration	SEC-04	Time to configure a new security and privacy mechanisms in an holocommunication for the deployment of 6G application
KPI-03	Bandwidth & Latency	SEC-03, SEC-04	Maximum data transfer rate (bandwidth) and the amount of delay (latency) that occurs when data is transmitted
KPI-04	System Resource Optimization	SEC-01, SEC-04	Measures the efficiency of the system in managing and optimizing its computational power, memory usage, and

			storage utilization.
KPI-05	Security & Privacy Coverage	SEC-05, SEC-06	Every component of a 6G application deployment is safeguarded by at least one element of the security and privacy mechanisms in place, reducing the risk of vulnerabilities and potential breaches.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, this report has examined the emerging technologies of holoportation and Virtual Reality (VR) within the context of 6G environments. This technology has the potential to revolutionise conferencing by enhancing its security, reliability, and speed.

We have also taken into account potential issues that may arise, such as concerns regarding trust and privacy when sharing data during holo-conferencing. We have outlined the necessary steps for setting up and conducting a session, as well as how the various components interact with each other. The report has outlined the necessary requirements for the technology to function effectively and has also provided insights on how to determine if it's functioning optimally. The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will assist us in verifying whether the system is fulfilling its requirements during the testing phase.

This report serves as a comprehensive guide to holoportation and virtual reality (VR) in 6G environments. This highlights the significance of addressing these issues to fully utilise the potential of this technology in the times to come. We will continue to work on improving this technology to better meet our needs.

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